

DIPL MICS

Human WGS method development on the P24: Sample Submission Form

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*Please complete the form below, attach all required documents and return to
shane.murray@diplomics.org.za*

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Introduction

DIPLOMICS is an 'Omics' (Genomics, Proteomics/Metabolomics and Bioinformatics) technology resource for researchers in South Africa and aims to:

- i) Create and maintain a world-class infrastructure in South Africa for Omics research.
- ii) Support the generation, analysis and application of good quality Omics data.
- iii) Support training of students and researchers in Omics technology.

To support these objectives, DIPLOMICS has purchased a PromethION 24 for their Genomics Training Lab, with the objective of developing methods for long-read whole genome sequencing of both human and non-human samples. DIPLOMICS is recruiting human samples for this initiative, which will run from 1 September 2023-31 August 2024.

By submitting samples for sequencing under this method development initiative, the Sample Contributor acknowledges the following:

- To provide high-quality DNA and quality control (QC) metrics, as indicated below. The cost of DNA extraction will be borne by the contributor
- To provide ethics documents pertaining to the DNA samples. DNA sample names may be decoded.
- To give consent to DIPLOMICS to transfer sequencing data to the Centre for High Performance Computing (CHPC). DIPLOMICS, through CLARITY, will use this data for evaluation of genome assembly pipelines which will be recorded on the DIPLOMICS Methods Zenodo community (under development). DIPLOMICS will also make the sequencing data available to the Sample Contributor (pod5/fast5 and FASTQ files).
- The Sample Contributor further acknowledges that the data will belong to them/their institution and that they can use the data and publish any findings arising from the data.
- The Sample Contributor confirms that they will acknowledge DIPLOMICS, DIRISA and the DSI in all presentations and publications using sequencing data and/or arising from their samples.
- The Sample Contributor will comply with all DSI reporting requests from DIPLOMICS (for example, student training using the methods developed through this initiative)
- The Sample Contributor gives consent to DIPLOMICS to publicize the methods developed through generating sequencing data for their samples. This will be done, for example, by means of conference or a report published on our website or other media channels.

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Contact Details

Title, name and surname:	
Affiliation / Organisation:	
Email address:	
Contact number:	
Address:	

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DNA Sample submission (add excel sheet as addendum with these column headings if >6 samples)

- Provide an aliquot of the eluate (50 ul) for in-house QC
- DNA samples must be submitted in DNA low-binding tubes
- Attach images of agarose gels / TapeStation results.

How many DNA samples are being submitted? _____

How will the samples be transported/delivered to 108 Albert Road, Woodstock, Cape Town? _____

#	Sample ID	Species	Tissue source	Extraction method / kit. Please note any deviations	Specify eluate and volume (ul) of sample	Qubit concentration (ng/ul)	Nanodrop 260/280	Nanodrop 260/230	Agarose Gel / TapeStation (Yes/No)	Average fragment size
1										
2										
3										
4										
5										
6										

Quality control disclaimer: If submitted DNA samples do not meet the quality control requirements (>1µg of dsDNA as measured by Qubit, purity ratios as measured by Nanodrop of A260/A280 = 1,8 and A260/A230 between 2 and 2,2, and average fragment size >10kb as measured by TapeStation, gel or equivalent), and these samples do not perform optimally in the assay and application, DIPLOMICS may not be able to proceed with the sequencing reaction, and cannot guarantee the sequencing outcome

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Permits and Ethics

NB! Detail the permits(s) and ethics required to collect and process these samples (*Please attach the supporting documents*)

Fate of samples

Please tick the appropriate box indicating what DIPLOMICS should do with remaining DNA samples after completion of analysis?

- Return to contributor Discard

Receipt of Sequencing Data

DIPLOMICS will make the sequencing data from your samples available to you (pod5/fast5 and FASTQ files). **How would you like to receive the sequencing data?**

- Via the Centre for High Performance Computing (CHPC)
 On a hard drive*

Other (detail: _____)

**If you select via hard drive, please provide a hard drive long with your sample submission.*

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Checklist

(X)	Item*
	Signed Material Transfer Agreement (MTA) (if required by your institution)
	Copy of supporting permits attached
	Copy of ethics approval attached
	Agarose / TapeStation images
	Aliquot of eluate provide
	Indicated how you would like to receive the sequencing data
	Signed sample submission form

*Indicate NA where required.

Delivery Details

Samples delivered by:

Name and surname

Date

Signature

Samples received by:

Name and surname

Date

Signature

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Signatures

By signing below, you acknowledge you have read and understood all the terms and conditions listed in this document:

Sample Contributor/ Principal Investigator:

Name and surname

Date

Signature

Position

Institution

Department

E-mail address

Tel-No

Alternative E-mail address

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For DIPLOMICS use only

#	Sample ID (see Part A or B):	DIPLOMICS Sample Code (for REDCap)	Sample storage location
1			
2			
3			
4			
5			
6			
7			
8			

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Version history

Version	Date Modified	Significant changes	Changes made by	Next review date
0.1	15-09-2023	Document created	S Murray	
0.2	21-07-2024	Project dates edited	S Murray	

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DOI: Zenodo DIPLOMICS Methods Community (*to be added*)

